

THE APPARENT DISSOCIATION CONSTANTS OF DIETHYLDITHIOCARBAMIC ACID

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Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is found to be a diacidic base, diethyldithiocarbamic acid being an ampholyte. The values of the two acidic dissociation constants, as found out by Bjerrum's method, by E.M.F. measurements, are: $pK_1 = 7.5$ (-SH group) and $pK_2 = 8.4$ [$-NH^+(C_2H_5)_2$].

Sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is a well-known reagent for the colorimetric estimation of copper (Callan and Henderson, *Analyst*, 1929, 54, 650; Hoar, *ibid.*, 1937, 62, 657). The corresponding acid is unstable and has not been isolated (Heilbron and Bunbury, "Dictionary of Organic Compounds," published by Eyre and Spottiswoode, 1953, Vol. II, p. 184). According to Martin (*Anal. Chem.*, 1953, 25, 1260), the acid is unstable at pH 1 to 3. The dissociation constant of the acid has been found polarographically to be of the order of 10^{-7} (Sartori and Calzolari, *Chem. Abs.*, 1952, 46, 6968). Its value is found polarographically in 60% ethanol to be 2.9×10^{-6} (Gregg and Tyler, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 72, 4561).

EXPERIMENTAL

Conductometric and pH methods were employed for the investigation. The sodium salt was of A.R. quality of B.D.H. company. All other chemicals used were either A.R. or similar quality. Conductivity measurements were made at $35^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$, employing the Leeds and Northrup assembly. pH measurements were made at 30° by a Beckman pH meter, model H-2. Suitable buffers were employed to standardise the pH meter. Solutions of 1, 2, 5 and 10 mM/litre of the substance were prepared*by direct weighing and titrated against standard acids of suitable concentration either conductometrically or by pH measurements. Solutions of 25 or 50 c.c. aliquots were employed and different amounts of acid added. It was found that there was a continuous shift in the observations which became steady only after 24 hours. Hence, a uniform procedure was adopted in which aliquot solutions with different amounts of acid added were kept at room temperature for 24 hours before measurements were made.

Conductivity Measurement

Suitable aliquots (25 or 50 c.c.) of 1, 2, 5 and 10 milimolar solutions of the sodium salt were titrated against perchloric, hydrochloric and acetic acids of suitable normalities. The typical curve of

each of the acids is shown in Fig. 1, curves 1-3. The resistances were corrected for the volume change. The curves are drawn of resistances against c.c. of titrant added.

FIG. 1

Curve No.	Scale-axis.		Reagent.		Acid used.	End-point.	
	X 1 unit = c.c.	Y 1 unit = ohms.	mM.	c.c. taken.		Required.	Obtained.
1	1	250	1	50	0.02633 N-HCl	3.80	3.80
2	0.5	50	5	50	0.2550 N-HAc	1.96	2.00
3	1	25	10	50	0.2340 N-HClO ₄	4.27	4.30

pH Measurement

The above solutions were also utilised for *pH* measurements. The conductometric titrations show that the corresponding acid formed is a dibasic one. This has also been confirmed by this method. The end-point was obtained when nearly double the equivalents of the titrant acid was added. Some typical observations and three curves, one with each acid, are recorded in Table I and in Fig. 2 (curves 4-6).

TABLE I

Acid.	Normality.	mM of Na-salt.	pK_1 .	pK_2 .
HCl	0.00884	1	7.4	8.5
HCl	0.0884	10	7.5	8.7
HCl	0.1050	2	7.7	8.6
HCl	0.1050	5	7.4	8.4
HClO ₄	0.0234	1	7.5	8.3
HClO ₄	0.2340	10	7.4	8.2
CH ₃ COOH	0.2550	5	7.7	8.4
CH ₃ COOH	0.2550	10	7.5	8.3

FIG. 2.

Curve No.	mM.	Reagent.		Acid used.	End-point.	
		c.c. taken.			Required.	Obtained.
4	1	50		0.02340N-HClO ₄	4.27	4.30
5	5	50		0.2633N-HCl	1.90	1.90
6	10	50		0.2550N-HAc	3.92	3.90

DISCUSSION

Both pH and conductometric measurements have shown that sodium diethyldithiocarbamate is a diacidic base. This has not been apparently reported before. We shall first consider the E.M.F. data. When 50 c.c. of 0.005*M* of the sodium salt is neutralised by 0.2633*N*-HCl, sharp inflection is obtained on addition of 1.90 c.c. of the acid (Fig. 2, curve 5). This gives the normality of the sodium salt 0.01, $[(0.2633 \times 1.9)/50]$; since molarity of the salt is 0.005, it is obvious that the salt is diacidic. In Fig. 2 (curves 4-6) the *X*-axis represents c.c. of 0.02340*N*-HClO₄, 0.2633*N*-HCl, and 0.2550*N*-CH₃COOH, added to 50 c.c. of 1, 5, and 10 *mM* of the sodium salt respectively. If instead of c.c., equivalents of the acids added were plotted, the graphs would have clearly shown that in each case a sharp inflection had occurred when two equivalents of the acids were added. However, present method of graphical representation appears preferable, as in the latter case all the three curves will fall almost on the same line before neutralisation.

Similarly, a careful consideration of the conductivity data reveals the same point, *i.e.*, two equivalents of the acid are required for complete neutralisation. 50 c.c. of 0.001*M* sodium salt requires 3.80 c.c. of 0.02633*N*-HCl (Fig. 1, curve 1), when a sharp inflection is observed. On the other hand, it has been observed that when one equivalent of the acid is added, the inflection point is not predominant. This is due to pK_1 and pK_2 differing by about one unit only.

pK_1 and pK_2 have been determined, following Bjerrum's method (Bjerrum, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941). According to Bjerrum, pK_1 and pK_2 are obtained when the acid is 1/4 and 3/4 neutralised respectively. The values of pK_1 and pK_2 are shown in Table I. The sodium salt on treating with acid changes its conductance or pH slowly and becomes ultimately diacidic. This change may be represented as:

Diethyldithiocarbamic acid may be represented as:

The behaviour of this acid may be compared with those of ampholytes. In this case -SH is an acidic group and -NEt₂ is a basic one. The conjugate acid of the basic group will be -NH⁺Et₂. Therefore two acidic groups, dissociation constants of which are found out in the present case, will be -SH and -NH⁺(C₂H₅)₂, and the corresponding dibasic acid will be as represented by (1). By analogy with tertiary aliphatic amines, NH⁺(C₂H₅)₂ may be considered to be a weaker acidic group ($pK_2=8.4$) and -SH may be considered to be the stronger one ($pK_1=7.5$).

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